

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of 2-Acetyl 1-Naphthol with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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The interaction of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol with bivalent metal ions Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and some oxycations VO(II) and UO₂(II) were investigated potentiometrically in 50% V/V acetone-water mixture. The stability constants were determined by Bjerrum's method as adopted by Calvin and Wilson at 35° and an ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M$ KNO₃. The order of metal chelates is as follows:

VERY little work has been reported on the metal chelates of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol. Van Uitert and Fernelius reported the stability constants of metal chelates of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol with Cu(II), Mg(II) and Ni(II) in 75% dioxan medium. The present communication deals with the potentiometric study of the metal chelates of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol with Mn(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and some oxycations like VO(II) and UO₂(II) in 50% V/V acetone-water mixture at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1M KNO₃.

Materials and Methods

2-Acetyl 1-naphthol was prepared by the literature method². The acetone was of AR grade. Metal salt solutions were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water and the metal contents were determined by standard procedures. Carbonate free potassium hydroxide was prepared and standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate.

An ELICO pH meter Model LI-10 having ELICO Glass and Calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements. The electrode system was calibrated with standard buffers pH 4 and 9.00. The pH regions below 3.5 and above 10.5 were calibrated by measurements in HCl and NaOH solutions from the data tabulated by Harned and Owen³. The solutions were prepared in 50% acetone-water mixture using CO₂ free distilled water.

The experimental method employed consists of potentiometric titration of the ligand (HA) with standard KOH solution in the absence and in the presence of metal ion being investigated. The ionic strength was maintained constant by using 0.1M KNO₃ as the supporting electrolyte. The dilute solutions of the ligand and metal ion were taken in a double wall jacketed glass cell through which water from a thermostat was circulated. The temperature within the cell could be maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Once the solution attained the required temperature the solutions were titrated with standard alkali from a calibrated 5 ml. microburette. In order to avoid the dilution effect the alkali used was much more concentrated than the acid.

The pH in 50% V/V acetone-water mixture was calculated from the following relationship⁴

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H \quad \dots (1)$$

where $B =$ pH meter reading, and $\log U_H$ conversion factor.

The conversion factor $\log U_H$ was obtained from the difference between the observed pH value 'B' and the theoretical value $-\log [H^+]$. The theoretical value of $-\log [H^+]$ was calculated taking into the activity coefficients into account. 'B' value was obtained by taking aliquot quantity of 0.01M HCl in 50% of acetone.

The pH titrations were carried out by introducing free ligand and 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratios of metal ion to ligand concentrations into a titration cell. The pH readings were taken after the addition of small increments of alkali. The solutions were clear upto the pH 7.00 in the case of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), and Zn(II). The precipitation starts after pH 5.5 in the case of VO(II) and UO₂(II). The stability constants were calculated from the pH values taken below the precipitation point.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constant for 2-acetyl 1-naphthol (HA) was calculated by Henderson's equation. The dissociation constant is related to the usual equilibrium expression by the following expression

In order to determine the stability constant of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes formed during the titration of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 mixture of metal ion and ligand the following equations are used :

The chelate stability constants were calculated from 1 : 2 titration curve by an adoption of Bjerrum's method as followed by Calvin and Wilson⁵ employing the final equation

$$\bar{n} = \frac{1}{C_M} [aC_A + H^+ - A^-]$$

where

C_M = Total concentration of metal ion,

C_A = Total concentration of the ligand,

a = equivalents of alkali added per mole of the ligand and A^- was calculated by the following equation

$$A^- = \frac{K_a}{H^+} [C_A - aC_A + H^+]$$

The $\bar{n}$ values obtained at different pH values are plotted against pA^- for different metal ions (Fig. 1). The stability constant K_1 which is equivalent to pA^- at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ was taken from the formation curve. Thus obtained stability constants K_1 at 35° and $\mu = 0.1M$ KNO_3 are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. A plot of $\bar{n}$ versus $\log 1/A^-$ for different metal ions.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 2-ACETYL 1-NAPHTHOL WITH DIFFERENT METAL IONS IN 50% ACETONE-WATER MIXTURE AT 35°, $\mu = 0.1M$ KNO₃

Sl. No.	Metal ion	Log <i>K</i>
1.	H ⁺	10.42
2.	Mn(II)	4.60
3.	Co(II)	5.16
4.	Ni(II)	5.42
5.	Cu(II)	7.81
6.	Zn(II)	6.62
7.	VO(II)	9.08
8.	UO ₂ (II)	9.14

The values of log *K*₁ at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1*M* KNO₃ are presented in Table 1. The stability constants are in the order of Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II)

< Cu(II) > Zn(II) < VO(II) < UO₂(II). A plot of log *K* for transitional elements against the second ionization potential gave a linear relationship.

Further details of these investigations will be published subsequently.

References

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